

Evidence-Based Toxicology

Declaration of Related Interests Form

This version: 23 January 2025

Guidance Notes

The purpose of this form is to support clear and comprehensive declaration of author interests in relation to journal submissions. Please note this form is not for disclosing conflicts of interest, as most journals require. It is for general disclosure of interests related to the submitted work. The reasons for this approach are explained in the following.

(1) Interests matter because they have the potential to disrupt or compromise decision-making in a research project. Interests therefore need to be disclosed and, if they constitute a conflict of interest, they need to be managed.

(2) An interest is any commitment, obligation, duty or goal associated with a particular social role or practice that relates to the commitments, obligations, duties, or goals associated with the particular work being described in a submission to Evidence-Based Toxicology.

(3) Related interests may be financial or non-financial. Declarations of related interests are essential in enabling editors and peer-reviewers to evaluate how effectively submitting authors have managed their interests in relation to their research goals.

(4) Having or declaring a related interest is not the same thing as having a conflict of interest. A conflict of interest arises when serving one interest could involve working at the expense of another interest. Conflicts of interest need to be managed by researchers in order to preserve the integrity of decision-making in a study.

(5) Contributors to a research project should declare all related interests that a reasonable person would want to know about to be confident that the interests that relate to the submitted work are known about, and can therefore be evaluated for having been appropriately managed.

(6) It is unlikely that someone with no interests in relation to a project would still be interested in being involved in a project. Declaring no interests is therefore unlikely to be a valid response to the questions in this form.

(7) Interests that cannot contractually be declared need not be described in detail, but their existence must be noted. If the contract specifies that not even the presence of a contractual limitation can be declared, the author should state they are unable to complete the form.

Author information

Name: Kyoungtae Kim

Date: 12/15/2025

Title of manuscript: A PIECE OF THE ECOTOXICOLOGY PUZZLE: HOW CAN CURRENT AND FUTURE RESEARCH INFORM PPD REGULATIONS?

Contribution to the Publication

Please agree this with the senior authors and describe in CRediT format if possible

Kyoungtae Kim: Review, editing, and supervision

Interests

Please select "Yes" or "No" next to any interests below that are relevant to your situation

Financial interests		Non-financial interests	
Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by your submitted publication?		Do you have any of the following interests that could potentially influence or be affected by your submitted publication?	
<input type="checkbox"/> NO	From employment or provision of services, such as directorships, consultancy, honoraria, etc.	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	Deeply held beliefs or convictions
<input type="checkbox"/> NO	From intellectual property, such as patents, copyrights, etc.	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	Current and previous research findings or projects
<input type="checkbox"/> NO	From investments such as shares, stocks, other financial instruments, etc.	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	Commitments to specific standards or processes
<input type="checkbox"/> NO	From litigation or legal cases	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	Publicly held positions
<input type="checkbox"/> NO	From grants	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	Personal relationships
<input type="checkbox"/> NO	Other financial interests	<input type="checkbox"/> NO	Membership or active role in other organisations, e.g. societies, lobby or pressure groups, government agencies, etc.
		<input type="checkbox"/> NO	Position of authority in an organisation, such that you may be seen as upholding that organisation's views, standards, values, etc.
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Author information

Name: Emma Braun

Date: 12/15/2025

Title of manuscript: A PIECE OF THE ECOTOXICOLOGY PUZZLE: HOW CAN CURRENT AND FUTURE RESEARCH INFORM PPD REGULATIONS?

Contribution to the Publication

Please agree this with the senior authors and describe in CRediT format if possible

Emma Braun: Conceptualization, Visualization, Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing

Interests

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YES	From employment or provision of services, such as directorships, consultancy, honoraria, etc.	NO	Deeply held beliefs or convictions
NO	From intellectual property, such as patents, copyrights, etc.	YES	Current and previous research findings or projects
NO	From investments such as shares, stocks, other financial instruments, etc.	NO	Commitments to specific standards or processes
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Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

Submitting this manuscript for publication may aid in my attaining a job once I graduate with my masters degree.

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

Completing this commentary has aided in my research on 6PPD and 6PPD-Q and their toxic effects in fungal cells and mammalian cell lines.

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Author information

Name: Mileah Metcalf

Date: 12/15/2025

Title of manuscript: A PIECE OF THE ECOTOXICOLOGY PUZZLE: HOW CAN CURRENT AND FUTURE RESEARCH INFORM PPD REGULATIONS?

Contribution to the Publication

Please agree this with the senior authors and describe in CRediT format if possible

Mileah Metcalf: Conceptualization, Visualization, Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing

Interests

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Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

The acceptance of this publication may help bolster my resume and help me secure a medical school acceptance.

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

Completing this commentary has aided in my understanding of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q and I have been involved in a research project investigating their toxic effects in fungal cells.